

Couples' Agreement & Disagreement on Fertility Preferences: A Comparative Study of Indonesia and Bangladesh

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Abstract

Couples' decision making on reproductive health preferences and outcomes are a complex phenomenon. Any program that intended exclusively for men or women may fail because the sexual and reproductive decisions are to be potentially made by both the partners. The ICPD document recognizes that couples are a unit. ICPD Cairo conference 1994 recognizes Gender perspective and taking reproductive decisions is a recently developed concept, which is more focused after ICPD Cairo conference 1994. This study is going to contribute towards couples' fertility preferences and the factors that determine such preferences in two Muslim countries Indonesia and Bangladesh. In both the countries, the Total Fertility Rate is close to each other, but the other socio-economic and demographic parameters vary significantly. This study tries to explain the determinants of couples' fertility preferences in two Muslim dominated countries having different socio-economic, cultural, and demographic background. The view towards ideal number of children is higher among the wives in Bangladesh whereas the same view is higher among the husbands in Indonesia with respect to their partners' view for the same. Women exposure to mass media has emerged as an important variable in building couples' agreement for ideal number of children in both the countries. The couples' agreement on ideal number of children is emerging as an important determinant of contraceptive use with respect to those couples that are not in agreement for the same in both the countries

Keywords

Couples, Agreement, Disagreement, Fertility, Preferences.

Introduction

Couples' reproductive decisions are a complex phenomenon where the husband and wife take reproductive and sexual health decisions sometimes individually and sometimes jointly. Any program that intended exclusively for men or women may fail because the sexual and reproductive decisions are to be potentially made by both the partners. The ICPD document recognizes that couples are a unit. ICPD Cairo conference 1994 recognizes Gender perspective and taking reproductive decisions is a recently developed concept, which is more focused after ICPD Cairo conference 1994. The couples live in a society where their sexual and reproductive decisions are many times driven by the Father-in-law / Mother-in-law, relatives, neighbors, and friends. The couples may face challenges when his/her spouse is not in agreement for the sexual and reproductive decisions. For example, if women say that she does not want child and willing to use contraceptive to avoid pregnancy but fail to protect because her husband may want to have child and against of using the contraceptive. Therefore, the inter-spousal communication and agreement-disagreement between husband and wife for reproductive and sexual decisions drew attention for the researcher. Studies undertaken in various research reported that a low level of communication between husband and wife may lead to increase in family size, unwanted pregnancies, low level of contraceptive use and abortion cases.

This study is going to contribute towards the couples' fertility preferences and the factors that determine such preferences, but the specialty of the study is to understand the phenomenon in two different Muslim dominated countries with having different socio-economic backgrounds. Indonesia and Bangladesh are having different kinds of socio-

economic background, but the fertility decline drastically during the last three decades in both the countries. (Jones, 11977) During the same period Indonesia had seen much social and economic progress whereas Bangladesh was having very slowly way of progress.

In spite of these differences between the two countries the TFR of Indonesia (2.2, 2024) and Bangladesh (1.9, 2024) are following the similar trends despite the varied socio-economic and geographic differences between the two Muslim countries. To be precise, Bangladesh has lower TFR than Indonesia even though Indonesia is having better socio-economic status than Bangladesh. Therefore, it has become important to understand the couples' fertility preferences in two different kinds of socio-economic & cultural environment. Whether these backgrounds related differences are really contributing towards couples' fertility preferences and, in turn, completed family size or some other factors are playing crucial role in this direction. In this study, the couple is treated as the unit of analysis and their fertility preferences are measured based on crucial background variables.

Objective of study

The main objectives of the present paper are to compare the impact of socio-economic and demographic factors in determining the couples' fertility preferences in both the countries. However the specific objectives of the paper are;

1. To compare the couples' fertility preferences in Indonesia and Bangladesh.
2. To study the impact of socio-economic and demographic factors on couples' fertility preferences in both the countries.

Review of Literature

Gender perspective and taking reproductive decisions is a recently developed concept, which is more focused after ICPD Cairo conference 1994. There are a few studies conducted to understand the couples' reproductive decision-making process and their respective fertility preferences to determine the completed family size. Although the desired family size may not be an adequate proxy for completed fertility but the desired numbers are a fairly good predictor of completed family size. Becker has done an inter-continental study of Asia, Africa, Europe and USA and concluded that the reproductive health interventions that target couples are found to be more effective than those directed to only one sex. (Becker et al.1996).

A study conducted by using DHS data collected from 18 developing countries between 1990 and 1996 to explore and compare the husbands' and wives' attitudes toward fertility and contraception. Men and women in these countries desire fairly large families, however, husbands tend to want more children than their wives and do want the next child sooner. (Bankole et al. 1998)

Methodology

The Demographic Health Survey data 2004 is used for this study. In both the countries information were collected from males and females. Only Muslim couples are used from the files because both the countries are having Muslim dominated population and we wanted to see the couples' fertility preferences within the same religion but having different kinds of socio-economic, demographic and cultural environment. The total sample size of couple file was 2873 for Bangladesh and 7684 for Indonesia but in this study only Muslim couples are used as the unit of analysis. Therefore, the actual sample size included in this study is 2551 couples from Bangladesh and 6402 couples from Indonesia.

To measure the differences in couples' fertility preferences only a few questions are taken for further analysis, which is asked from both the partners. These variables are further computed as a couple variables to compare the level of concordance between the spouses. Further, these variables are classified into three categories, namely, the desire is 'higher among husbands', 'same for both', 'higher among wives'. These categorized comparative responses are as follows-

- a. Husbands' response > Wives' response (H>W)
- b. Husbands' response = Wives' response (H=W)
- c. Husbands' response < Wives' response (H< W)

Independent variables for the study are classified in three major groups for statistical analysis;

- a. Demographic variables – Current age of women, Children ever born, Difference in couples' age & marital duration.
- b. Socio-economic variables- Place of residence, Women's education, Difference in Couples' education & Wealth index.
- c. Exposure variables – Women exposure to mass media, Discussion of family planning with partners, Women's mobility.

Result and Discussion**Background Characteristics**

The background characteristics of the study are mainly divided into three major groups consisting of Socio-economic, demographic & exposure variables. The demographic characteristics includes in this study are current age of women, couples' age difference, children ever born and marital duration. The socio-economic variables are wealth index, women's education, difference in couples' education and type of place of residence. The exposure variable includes the women's mobility, mass media exposure and discussion of family planning with partners.

The percentages of women below age 25 are higher in Bangladesh than that of Indonesia. The difference in couples' age is less in Indonesia as compared to Bangladesh. The marital duration, children ever born, contraceptive use and mean children ever born are almost similar in both the countries. The socio-economic variables, women education and difference in couples' education are higher in Indonesia compared to Bangladesh. Women's exposure to mass media is higher in Indonesia than Bangladesh.

Couples' Agreement and Disagreement on Ideal Number of Children by Background Characteristics

The Table – 1 exhibits couple's agreement and disagreement for ideal number of children by children ever born. The couples' agreement is observed higher among less than 25 years age group as compared to other age groups in both the countries. As marital duration increases the couples' agreement on ideal number of children decreases in both the countries. The couples' agreement on ideal number of children is found to be higher up to two parity as compared to three and above parities in both the countries. The type of place of residence does not have any role in determining couples' agreement on ideal number of children in both the countries. The female education and wealth index plays an important role in building couples' agreement on ideal number of children in both the countries but the couples' educational difference is found to be important in Bangladesh not in Indonesia for the same. Women exposure to mass media is important in building couples' agreement on ideal number of children whereas women's mobility does not have any role for the same in both the countries.

Table- 1: Couples' agreement and disagreement on ideal number of children by background characteristics

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Background Characteristics		Bangladesh				Indonesia			
		W>H	W=H	H>W	Total	W>H	W=H	H>W	Total
Current age of woman	< 25 years	22.2	62.6	15.2	929	17.6	57.9	24.5	1021
	25 to 34 years	25.0	56.9	18.1	999	18.8	54.0	27.2	2163
	35 to 49 years	29.2	49.8	21	428	21.3	49.8	28.9	1879
Marital duration	0 - 5 years	20.5	63.7	15.8	487	16.3	58.4	25.3	1246
	6 - 10 years	25.4	59.3	15.3	531	18.3	56.1	25.5	1108
	> 10 years	25.9	55.2	19.0	1338	21.4	49.6	28.9	2709
Difference in Couples' age	< & = 5 years	25.5	59.2	15.3	530	20.1	54.1	25.8	3284
	6 - 10 years	24.9	56.4	18.7	974	18.1	53.5	28.4	1385
	11 & above years	23.8	58.7	17.5	852	19.5	45.2	35.3	394
Children ever born	<= 2	21.6	64.3	14.1	1282	17.2	58.5	24.3	3107
	3 & above	28.3	50.2	21.5	1074	23.1	44.8	32.1	1956
Place of residence	Rural	24.8	56.7	18.5	1518	19.9	52.8	27.4	2770
	Urban	24.3	60.0	15.7	838	19.1	53.8	27.2	2293
Female education	No education	28.3	49.5	22.2	891	23.9	45	31.2	218
	Up to primary	22.2	59.7	18.1	744	21.1	51.5	27.4	2486
	Up to Secondary & above	22.7	66.3	11.0	721	17.4	55.8	26.8	2359
Couples' education	Both are illiterate	28.5	47.9	23.6	466	24.6	54.1	21.3	61
	Either husband or wife is illiterate	26.2	53.3	20.4	690	20.6	45.3	34.2	243
	Both are literate	22.3	64.3	13.4	1200	19.4	53.6	27.0	4759
Wealth index	Poorest	26.8	48.2	24.9	485	20.5	49.2	30.3	1318
	Poorer	23.1	57.4	19.5	493	19.1	54.1	26.8	998
	Middle	26.2	57.9	15.9	447	17.9	54.7	27.5	885
	Richer	25.9	59.1	15.0	394	20.5	55.1	24.4	860
	Richest	22.0	65.9	12.1	537	19.2	54.8	26.0	1002
Women exposure to mass media	Less exposure	27.6	52.9	19.5	1208	20.9	48.2	30.9	803
	More exposure	21.6	63.0	15.4	1148	19.2	54.1	26.6	4263
Women's mobility	No participation	25.4	57.8	16.8	1053	20.3	53.3	27.4	610
	Participation	24.1	57.9	18.0	1303	19.4	53.2	27.4	4453
Total		24.6	57.9	17.5	2356	19.5	53.2	27.3	5063

Logistic Regression Result for Contraceptive Use

The purpose of doing logistic regression for the contraceptive use as dependent variable is not to find the prime determinants of contraceptive use in Indonesia and Bangladesh but to find out the linkages between the contraceptive use and the couples' agreement on ideal number of children. Therefore, the interpretation of the Table-2 will be confined to only this variable.

The regression result has shown that there is very high likelihood for using contraceptives among the couples that are having agreement on ideal number of children by 1.356 times higher in Bangladesh and 1.203 times higher in Indonesia with respect to those couples that are not having agreement for the same. The couples' agreement for ideal number of boys is found to be insignificant in both the countries. Therefore, the couples' agreement for ideal number of children may play vital role in increasing contraceptive use in both the countries.

Table-2: Logistic regression for Couples' contraceptive use (0 = Disagreement, 1 = Agreement)

Background characteristics		Exp (β)	
		Bangladesh	Indonesia
Couples' agreement on ideal number of children	Disagreement@		
	Agreement	1.356***	1.203***
Couples' agreement on ideal number of boys	Disagreement@		
	Agreement	1.102	1.111

Current age of woman	< 25 years®		
	25 to 34 years	1.283	1.019
	35 to 49 years	1.123	0.649***
Marital duration	0 - 5 years®		
	6 - 10 years	1.811***	1.355***
	> 10 years	1.679***	1.395***
Difference in Couples' age	< & = 5 years®		
	6 - 10 years	1.024	1.005
	11 & above years	1.003	0.773
Children ever born	<= 2®		
	3 & above	1.290**	1.390***
Place of residence	Rural®		
	Urban	1.170	0.857**
Female education	No education®		
	Up to Primary	0.981	0.840
	Up to Secondary & above	1.198	0.711
Couples' education	Both are illiterate®		
	Either husband or wife is illiterate	1.019	1.135
	Both are literate	0.848	1.560
Wealth index	Poorest®		
	Poorer	1.116	1.420***
	Middle	1.035	1.480***
	Richer	1.130	1.523***
	Richest	1.046	1.407***
Women exposure to mass media	No exposure®		
	Exposure	1.102	1.172**

Discussed FP with partners	Never discussed [®]		
	Discussed	2.471***	2.866***
Women's mobility	No participation [®]		
	Participation	1.240**	1.093
<p>Note: * indicates significant at 10% i.e. p<0.1level, ** indicates significant at 5% i.e. p<0.05, *** indicates significant at 1% i.e. p<0.01</p>			

Conclusion

This study tries to explain the determinants of couples' fertility preferences in two Muslim dominated countries having different socio-economic, cultural and demographic background. The view towards ideal number of children is higher among the wives in Bangladesh whereas the same view is higher among the husbands in Indonesia with respect to their partners' view for the same. As far as mean ideal number of children is concerned, it is higher among the husbands and wives who are living in Indonesia than those of husbands and wives who are living in Bangladesh but in children ever born, it is found to be reverse in both the countries.

The demographic variables, children ever born has shown consistent finding with the couples' agreement on ideal number of children. As the number of children ever born increases from three and above parities, the couples' agreement for ideal number of children goes down with increasing parity. The socio-economic variables, namely wealth index and women's education play vital role in building couples' agreement on ideal number of children in Indonesia whereas couples' education and wealth index are crucial in Bangladesh. Women exposure to mass media has emerged as an important variable in building couples' agreement for ideal number of children in both the countries. Finally, the couples' agreement on ideal number of children is emerging as an important determinant of contraceptive use with respect to those couples that are not in agreement for the same in both the countries.

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